

SELF-STRETCHING VERSUS SELF-STRENGTHENING EXERCISES FOR NECK PAIN AND DISABILITY IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS WITH TEXT NECK SYNDROME: A THREE ARM CONTROLLED TRIAL

Nasir Mehmood^{*1}, Syed Areeb Muneer², Muhammada Zainab³, Ajneeha Fatima⁴,
Wajahat Sohail⁵, Saad Zafar⁶

^{*1,2,3,4,5,6}Department of Physical Therapy, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur

¹nasir.mehmood@iub.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Nasir Mehmood

Abstract

Background: Neck pain and forward head posture related symptoms due to smart phone and other such devices usage are increasingly observed and reported in university students, but there is a lack of definitive evidence regarding therapeutic value of simple self administered exercise strategies.

Objective: To compare effectiveness of self stretching versus self strengthening exercises on neck pain and disability in undergraduate students with text neck syndrome.

Methods: This experimental study was a three arm controlled trial conducted at Khawaja Fareed Campus of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan. 90 undergraduate students from different departments of Allied Health Sciences aged 18-25 years with daily screen time greater than 3 hours were assigned, in equal numbers, to self-strengthening (n = 30), self-stretching (n = 30) or control (n = 30) groups. The interventions were taught and trained to students who performed these exercises for 6 weeks as home based, self administered programs. Outcomes were collected before and after intervention i.e at the end of 6th week using a numerical pain rating scale (NPRS) and the Neck Disability Index (NDI).

Results: Both active interventions; self stretching and self strengthening significantly improved both outcomes. In the self strengthening group, mean daily neck pain decreased from 6.13 +/- 1.66 to 3.20 +/- 2.14 (p = 0.002) measured with NPRS and total NDI score improved from 17.17 +/- 8.40 to 8.27 +/- 7.09 (p = 0.001). In the self-stretching group, average daily neck pain decreased from 5.97 +/- 1.70 to 3.03 +/- 2.13 (p = 0.010) and total NDI score decreased from 16.77 +/- 7.52 to 9.57 +/- 6.48 showing a significant improvement (p=0.003). The control group results showed limited variation and its reduction in NDI was not statistically significant (p = 0.086). No significant between group difference was seen in post intervention total NDI score (p = 0.696), although stretching performed better on its work related item (p = 0.027).

Conclusion: Self stretching and self strengthening exercises both are feasible, low cost and clinically useful physiotherapy interventions for pain improvements among university students with text neck syndrome. None of the interventions demonstrated clear overall superiority across main outcomes, although both interventions gained significant superiority when compared with control group. So,

either exercise program can be selected pragmatically according to preference, compliance and individual needs.

INTRODUCTION

Neck pain is nowadays among most common musculoskeletal symptoms in young adults spending longer periods using smartphones, tablets and other handheld devices. Neck pain remains a major global source of disability and recent epidemiological studies state that its burden is continually increasing worldwide.[16,17] Within student and office populations, prolonged mobile/tablet usage, sustained cervical flexion postures and reduced physical activity levels have been identified as correlates of recurring somatic, psychological and behavioral symptoms.[4-7,18-21]

The term "Text Neck Syndrome" is now widely used to describe a group of symptoms related to sustained cervical flexion, forward head posture, upper body muscular overload and functional difficulty during or after smart phone/similar device usage. However, review of recent literature syntheses also note that the concept is not yet perfectly standardized and that "text neck" should be taken as a clinically useful term but still evolving label rather than a universally accepted and clearly defined diagnosis.[2,7,18] This strengthens the value of well structured physiotherapy intervention studies, as clinicians still need some easily workable, safe, evidence based and scalable approaches for this specific problem of a huge population.

Several mechanisms explain why and how smartphone overusage may provoke or perpetuate cervical symptoms. Prolonged neck flexion impacts load distribution negatively across the cervical spine, contributes to muscular fatigue and can increase strain on passive tissues with time.[19,20,24,25] Naturalistic posture monitoring studies have found that substantial head flexion (down tilt) is common during routine smartphone usage, reinforcing the biomechanical plausibility of exercise based treatment strategies.[24]

Exercise is a rational first line pathway in this regard because the common impairments associated with smartphone related neck pain are potentially modifiable. Stretching may address adaptive shortening and increased tone in muscles which are frequently subjected to overload in such postures,

including upper trapezius, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoid.[2,3,7] Strengthening, particularly in the form of cervical isometrics or stabilization exercises, may improve muscle activation, tolerance to sustained posture, develop muscle power generation ability and mechanical control of head and neck region.[2,3,8-10] Systematic reviews of therapeutic exercises for forward head posture and related upper body dysfunction generally support exercise as an effective option. However, they also show substantial heterogeneity in intervention design, duration, dosage and measured outcomes. [2,3] Most available evidence syntheses are multi-component and include posture education, scapular work, manual therapy interventions, neuromuscular facilitation techniques, supervised corrective exercise and so on. This makes it difficult to isolate the value of simple self-managed stretching or strengthening alone. [2,3,8-10]

That knowledge gap is especially relevant in poor resource settings. Self-administered exercises may be particularly of value in physiotherapy led campus health initiatives because they require little equipment, can be delivered to large student groups and are adaptable to home or hostel living. Comparative evidence base remains limited in this specific construct for this population. Some studies rhetorate superior effects of comprehensive corrective exercise programs over education or minimal care[8] whereas others report that different specific and limited exercise paradigms yield similar improvements in pain and disability.[2,3,9,10] The question of whether stretching or strengthening is more useful self management strategy for smartphone user students remains insufficiently studied and reported.

The primary aim of this study was to compare short term effects of home based self stretching and self strengthening exercises programs on neck pain and disability in university students with text neck syndrome. A secondary aim was to examine whether either intervention appeared preferable in selected symptom domains. We hypothesized that both self-administered exercise strategies would be associated

with significant within group improvement, whereas overall superiority of one intervention over the other would be limited. By focusing on feasible self-care interventions, the study was designed to generate clinically useful information for physiotherapists, university health programs and future trials in digitally active young adult populations.

Methods

Study design and setting

This study reports a single-center, three-arm, parallel-group controlled trial conducted at Khawaja Fareed Campus, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, Pakistan, between January 1 and May 31, 2025. 90 undergraduate students from different departments of Allied Health Sciences were included in the study having age 18-25 years, daily screen exposure greater than 3 hours, willingness to participate and symptoms of text neck syndrome. Exclusion criteria were previous trauma or surgery in neck region, any congenital deformity or systemic disease affecting the neck, neurological symptoms, hypermobility or hypomobility syndromes and current use of analgesic medication for neck pain. All participants provided voluntary informed consent and ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Review Committee of Department of Physical Therapy, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. Participants were allocated conveniently in equal numbers to 1 of 3 groups: self-strengthening exercise (Group A), self-stretching exercise (Group B), or control (Group C).

Interventions

Self-strengthening group

Group A performed a home based cervical isometric self strengthening exercise program for six weeks. Exercises included resisted neck flexion, extension, right and left side flexion and right and left rotation. Each contraction was held for 10 seconds and repeated 5 times. The program was prescribed twice daily and at least 5 days in a week. Intervention targeted the ability of cervical musculature to tolerate sustained load without visible joint movement, which is consistent with a pragmatic strengthening approach for students with neck posture related similar symptoms. [2,3,8-10]

Self-stretching group

Group B performed a six-week self stretching program targeting the upper trapezius, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoid. Each stretch was held for approximately 5 seconds with 10 repetitions twice a day at least 5 days a week. The selected muscles are commonly implicated in forward head posture and upper quarter tension patterns, hence making them appropriate targets in symptomatic smartphone users.[2,3,7-10]

Control group

Group C received no structured exercise intervention during the study period and the participants just continued their usual behavior without being involved in any stretching or strengthening activity.

Outcome measures

Neck pain was assessed with a Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), an 11-point self reportable scale ranging from 0 to 10, which remains a standard and reliable tool in neck pain research.[12-14] Neck disability was assessed using Neck Disability Index (NDI), a 10-item standardized questionnaire that captures disability across domains such as pain intensity, personal care, lifting, reading, headaches, concentration, work, driving, sleeping and recreation.[11,13,14] The NDI is one of the most established body region specific disability measures in cervical musculoskeletal studies and has demonstrated acceptable reliability, validity, and responsiveness across multiple neck pain populations.[11-14]

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed at SPSS v25.0. Within-group pre-post changes were evaluated using paired sample *t* tests. Post intervention between group comparisons were carried out using analysis of variance and independent sample comparisons where appropriate. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Ninety students completed the study dataset, with 30 participants in each group. The cohort was young (mean age 20.9years), predominantly females

(71.1%) and heavily exposed to screens. More than half of the participants reported at least 6 hours or more of daily screen usage and social media scrolling

was found to be most dominant activity during screen time. (Table-1; Figure-1)

Table-1: Baseline sample characteristics

Characteristic	Overall (n = 90)	Strengthening (n = 30)	Stretching (n = 30)	Control (n = 30)
Mean age, years	20.9	20.1	20.8	21.9
Female, n (%)	64 (71.1)	20 (66.7)	19 (63.3)	25 (83.3)
Screen use >6 h/day, n (%)	49 (54.4)	15 (50.0)	14 (46.7)	20 (66.7)
Primary screen activity = social media, n (%)	65 (72.2)	23 (76.7)	21 (70.0)	21 (70.0)

Figure-1: Daily screen-use duration across the full sample (n = 90).

The self strengthening group demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in average daily neck pain after six-week intervention completion, from 5.13 ± 1.66 to 2.20 ± 2.14 ($p = 0.005$), representing an absolute reduction of 2.93 points. The self stretching group also showed significant improvement, from 4.97 ± 1.56 to 2.73 ± 2.13 ($p = 0.009$), representing an absolute reduction of 2.24 points. In contrast, the control group changed from 5.30 ± 1.84 to 5.10 ± 2.07 , a numerical decrease of 0.20 points that did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.805$). (Figure-1) The two active groups ended up with significant post-intervention pain levels and between group comparison for average daily neck pain was not significant statistically ($p = 0.637$). (Table-2; Table-3)

Total NDI score lowered significantly in both intervention groups. In the self strengthening group, NDI fell from 17.17 ± 8.40 to 12.27 ± 7.09 ($p =$

0.001), showing an average reduction of 4.90 points. In the self stretching group, NDI decreased from 15.77 ± 8.62 to 11.57 ± 6.48 ($p = 0.003$), corresponding to an average reduction of 4.20 points. While in control group, NDI decreased from 14.40 ± 6.79 to 12.83 ± 6.37 , which was not statistically significant ($p = 0.086$). The post intervention between group comparison between the two active groups showed no statistically significant difference in total NDI score (12.27 ± 7.09 for strengthening vs 11.57 ± 6.48 for stretching; $p = 0.696$). (figure-3) Hence, best possible interpretation is that both strategies were similarly effective in improving overall neck disability after six weeks, while the control group did not show a comparatively robust statistical signal. (Table-2; Table-3)

Table-2: Primary outcomes before and after the 6-week intervention

Outcome	Group	Pre, mean ± SD	Post, mean ± SD	Absolute change	P value
Neck Pain	Strengthening	5.13 ± 1.66	2.20 ± 2.14	-2.93	0.005
Neck Pain	Stretching	4.97 ± 1.56	2.73 ± 2.13	-2.24	0.009
Neck Pain	Control	5.30 ± 1.84	5.10 ± 2.07	-0.50	0.805
NDI total score	Strengthening	17.17 ± 8.40	12.27 ± 7.09	-4.90	0.001
NDI total score	Stretching	15.77 ± 8.62	11.57 ± 6.48	-4.20	0.003
NDI total score	Control	14.40 ± 6.79	12.83 ± 6.37	-1.57	0.086

Figure-2: Average neck pain at pre and post intervention levels (after 6 weeks)

Figure-3: Mean total Neck Disability Index (NDI) score at pre and post intervention levels (after 6 weeks)

Table-3: Selected post-intervention comparison between the two active programs

Domain	Strengthening post mean ± SD	Stretching post mean ± SD	p value	Interpretation
Neck Pain	4.20 ± 2.14	3.93 ± 2.13	0.637	No significant difference
Pain-intensity	1.10 ± 1.00	1.63 ± 1.16	0.058	Trend favoring strengthening
Concentration	1.17 ± 1.09*	1.10 ± 0.96	0.066	Trend favoring stretching

Work item	1.43 ± 1.01	0.87 ± 0.78	0.027	Significant advantage for stretching
NDI total score	12.27 ± 7.09	11.57 ± 6.48	0.696	No significant difference

Self-strengthening also resulted in significant improvements in several secondary outcomes; including pain before bed, pain intensity, pain in lifting, pain while reading and pain in driving. The self-stretching group also improved significantly in pain before bed, pain in lifting, concentration and work. Other areas, e.g pain intensity, personal care, reading, headaches, driving, sleeping, and recreation, improved numerically but not significantly. The control group showed minimal change. Although sleeping was improved significantly, there were no significant improvements in average daily neck pain, pain before bed or total NDI scores indicating that some spontaneous variations occurred over six weeks but clearest improvement was seen in the exercise groups.

Discussion

This study compared two active physiotherapy exercise approaches; self stretching and self strengthening; for allied health sciences student smartphone users with text neck syndrome. Both programs significantly improved mean daily neck pain and total NDI scores after 6 weeks, whereas control group showed minimally convincing change and no significant improvement was seen in total disability. Neither of the active exercise approaches demonstrated clear overall superiority, although their item level effects differed somewhat: stretching appeared to benefit work-related function and concentration more while strengthening showed greater improvement in pain intensity related items. These findings are clinically very relevant because student health and physiotherapy services often need interventions which are simple, inexpensive, easy to perform and suitable for unsupervised performance. In situation, both self stretching and self strengthening appear to be reasonable first line options, without evidence supporting strict superiority between them.

These results are consistent with wider literature relating heavy smartphone use and forward head posture with neck pain and disability in young adults.[1,4-7,16-21] Recent student based studies also

associate such symptoms with prolonged device use, female gender, low physical activity and poor ergonomics, which resemble the risk profile of this cohort.[5,20,21] The intervention findings also fit in broader exercise evidence. Piruta and Kułak’s 2025 scoping review reported that physiotherapy interventions for text neck syndrome, including strengthening, stretching, corrective exercise and multimodal rehabilitation, can improve pain and other posture related symptoms, although the evidence remains limited in quality and consistency.[2] Similarly, a 2024 meta-analysis by Sepehri et al. supported therapeutic exercise for forward head posture and upper crossed syndrome related conditions, concluding that exercise based management can provide meaningful outcomes even when protocols differ.[3] Our findings match this pattern; exercise was beneficial but no decisive winner emerged between two simple self administered approaches.

Absence of a clear overall difference between stretching and strengthening is also consistent with comparative studies in forward head posture and neck pain populations, where different exercise approaches often produce similar short term improvements in pain and disability despite targeting different mechanisms.[9,10] Batool et al., for example, found that both neck stabilization and dynamic exercises improved pain and disability in patients with nonspecific neck pain and forward head posture, without any strong superiority of one method.[10] This supports the idea that once an exercise program reduces mechanical stress, improves movement behavior or enhances local muscular function, shared therapeutic effect may matter more than the exercise type itself. At the same time, some studies have reported more specific benefits from posture correction or corrective exercise packages, [8,23] while broader neck pain guidelines support exercise, education and self-management as key non-pharmacological strategies even when no single exercise type consistently dominates outcomes.[22]

The observed effects are biologically plausible too. Stretching may reduce tightness and guarding in

involved muscles such as the upper trapezius, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoid helping students move more comfortably and perform desk or device based assignments with less restriction.[2,3,7] This may explain the gains in concentration and work related function in stretching group. Strengthening, particularly cervical isometric work, may improve endurance, load tolerance and postural support during device usage. [2,3,9,10] This may explain why strengthening group improved more in pain intensity, reading, lifting and driving. In practical terms, the two approaches may act through somewhat different mechanisms, although their overall outcomes are similar.

An important feature of data analysis is that within-group improvements were more convincing than between-group differences, which is common in smaller rehabilitation studies. An accurate conclusion is that both active programs were associated with short-term benefit and neither showed clear overall superiority. The magnitude of NDI improvement also deserves a respectable attention; strengthening group improved by 4.9 points and stretching group improving by 4.2 points. Although thresholds for clinically meaningful change vary across settings, improvements in important activity domains, suggest meaningful symptom relief for majority of participants. [12-14]

The control group showed minimal numerical changes and a significant improvement in sleep despite no structured exercise. This may reflect natural symptom fluctuation, increased postural awareness after study participation, spontaneous behavioral adjustment or some noise in self-reported musculoskeletal outcomes. These factors do not negate the benefit of active interventions, but they do argue against oversimplified active versus control interpretation.

Strengths of the study

Despite its limitations, the study has several strengths. First, it addresses a clinically current problem in a genuinely high-risk population; undergraduate students with heavy smartphone use. Second, it evaluates two very pragmatic interventions that are realistic for self management and low resource physiotherapy practice. Third, the sample size of 90 is respectable for a student exercise study

and includes a control arm, which many small posture related trials lack. Fourth, the study used established patient reported outcomes rather than simple symptom descriptions, making the findings easier to interpret and compare with the wider neck pain literature. Finally, the direct comparison between self stretching and self strengthening adds useful knowledge to the field in which many interventions are bundled and are difficult to disentangle.

Limitations

The limitations are important and must be stated clearly.

First, the study was based on convenience recruitment from a single university campus, which limits external validity. The findings may not generalize to older adults, office workers, adolescents, or students from other educational and cultural settings. The sample was also predominantly female, which reflects a common pattern in neck pain research but may further affect generalizability.

Second, group allocation was not randomized with level of transparency expected in a contemporary quality randomized trial.

Third, outcome set was entirely self-reported. Although NPRS and NDI are valid and useful in neck pain research, they do not replace objective biomechanical measurement. The study did not assess craniovertebral angle, cervical range of motion, muscle endurance, posture during smartphone use or exercise adherence. This is very relevant because the two interventions may have differed biomechanically without producing clearly different self reported totals.

Fourth, no long-term follow-up was available, so sustainability of benefit is unknown. Given the chronic and behavior related nature of smartphone linked neck pain, short-term gains are important but insufficient.

Implications for physiotherapy practice

This study offers a practical clinical message. Physiotherapists working with students may not need to start with equipment based or highly supervised programs, as both simple self-stretching and basic self strengthening can relieve symptoms when taught clearly.

Recommendations

Future research should move beyond simple pre-post symptom reporting. Upcoming trials should include clear randomization methods, objective postural and functional outcomes, adherence monitoring and longer follow-up. It would also be useful to test combined approaches, such as stretching plus strengthening or exercise plus posture education, against single interventions. Given the scalability of digital health, app-supported or tele-supervised self management may be particularly relevant for students.

Conclusion

Among undergraduate university students with high smartphone exposure and symptoms of with text neck syndrome, both self stretching and self strengthening exercises were associated with significant short-term improvements in average daily neck pain and neck associated disability. Neither active exercise strategy demonstrated clear overall superiority. These findings support the use of simple, low-cost self management exercise programs in physiotherapy and student health settings.

Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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